

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight A444

27 March 1996

Satellite Calibration Validation

For more information contact:

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FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. A 444

DATE: 27 10 31 96

Take off: 10 30

Landing: 14 00

Aircraft Scientist : A. KAYE
Flight Leader : D PERCIVAL
Others : M PICKERING
 J HENT
 H GREENSMITH
 SF(26) C DONLAN
 SF(26) J CAIRNS

Captain : FLT LT M PURSE
Co-pilot : SQN LDR C O'BRIAN
Navigator : FLT LT J CANNING
Engineer : FLT SGT J LAM
Loadmaster : M-ENG K QUICK

Trials Instructions

Operating area : BRISTOL CHANNEL

General synoptic situation

TIME: 12 Z

FLIGHT REPORT A444 27/03/96 ATSR II CAL_VAL

Time 1	E.M.	Time 2	E.M.	Event	Height	Heading
08:12:43				OMEGA LAT/LONG For Start and End of Run Data On. Start Up at N51°09.83' W001°44.60'		
10:28:25				TAKE OFF BOSCOMBE DOWN		
				Climb to transit height heading towards Bristol Channel.		
10:52:09 (12)		11:13:38 (13)		Profile 1	FL260 4000'	290° 1000'/min
11:13:38 (13)		11:21:08 (14)		P 1 cont	4000' 50 ft	090° 500'/min
				N51°01.9' W004°12.3' to N51°08.0' W006°00.0' Sea State 5/6		
11:23:37 (15)		11:26:37 (16)		Run 1	100 ft	280°
				N51°00.6' W006°05.8' to N51°11.6' W006°19.7' Run abandoned to reposition due to cloud cov.r.		
11:37:47 (17)		11:41:03 (18)		Profile 2	FL070 4000'	180° 1000'/min
11:41:03 (18)		11:48:15 (19)		P 2 cont	4000' 50 ft	230° 500'/min
				N50°48.6' W005°53.4' to N51°19.0' W006°05.3' Sea State 4		
11:50:11 (20)		12:05:49 (21)		Run 2.1	100 ft	050°
				N50°20.5' W006°09.1' to N50°53.4' W005°21.2'		
12:09:48 (22)		12:20:23 (23)		Run 2.2	100 ft	220°
				N50°55.9' W005°35.5' to N50°30.1' W006°07.7'		
12:21:25 (24)		12:33:31 (25)		Run 3.1	1000'	060°
				N50°29.0' W006°05.9' to N50°52.9' W005°26.9'		
12:34:47 (26)		12:46:42 (27)		Run 3.2	1000'	240°
				N50°53.8' W005°30.3' to N50°29.8' W006°18.2'		
12:49:12 (28)		12:57:31 (29)		Profile 3.1	50 ft FL040	060° 500'/min
12:57:31 (29)		13:03:33 (30)		P 3.1 cont	FL040 FL100	270° 1000'/min
				N50°29.0' W006°16.3' to N49°38.0' W006°18.0' Sea State 4		
13:03:33 (30)		13:11:32 (31)		Run 4	FL100	270°
				N49°38.0' W006°18.0' to N50°53.4' W006°17.5'		
13:13:22 (32)		13:23:06 (33)		Profile 3.2	FL100 FL200	080° 1000'/min
				N50°51.0' W006°16.5' to N51°03.5' W005°26.3'		
13:23:06 (33)		13:31:11 (34)		Run 5	FL200	075°
				N51°03.5' W005°26.3' to N51°12.3' W004°40.1'		
13:31:11 (34)		13:41:22 (35)		Profile 3.3	FL200 FL300	100° 1000'/min
				N51°12.3' W004°40.1' to N51°15.0' W003°38.5'		
				Steep Descend into Boscombe Down		
13:57:50				LAND AT Boscombe Down		
14:03:14				Data off. Shut down at 51°09.88N 001°44.63W		

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne
Support Facility

Sea Surface Temperature and Aerosol Experiment

Date: 27/3/96

Flight No: A444

SORTIE OBJECTIVE: To provide a sea surface temperature and aerosol number density and mode size data for model validation and calibration for ATSR I/II.

LOCATION: South West approaches as dictated by location of satellite track as shown on attached map.

WEATHER: Clear sky conditions, no cirrus cloud although some cumulus clouds can be tolerated.

FLIGHT PATTERN: [1] Transit to operating area at suitable altitude.

Follow flight pattern as show in attached diagram. The runs should be timed such that the satellite passes over at about the mid-point of the 100 ft run.

- [2] High level run >F1200, 50-100 miles. (20 min)
- [3] Execute a profile from current level to 50 ft in cloud free air if possible. Profile at @1,000 ft/min down to top of boundary layer and then @500 ft/min to minimum safe altitude. (30 min)
- [4] 100 ft run along line of satellite track, >100 miles. Overpass occurs halfway along run. (35 minutes)
- [5] Reciprocal run at _____ ft at level of maximum aerosol concentration. (35 min)
- [6] Profile from 50 ft (or minimum safe altitude) at 500 ft/min to top of boundary layer and the @1,000 ft/min to flight level of original high level run (30 min)
- [7] High level run >F1200, 50-100 miles. (20 min)
- [8] Transit back to base.

TOTAL DURATION: 3 Hours on task

Sea Surface Temperature and Aerosol Experiment
Date: 27/3/96 Flight No: A444

Flight planning diagram

ATSR 1 - Wednesday 27 March
ATSR 2 - Thursday 28 March.

Western Approaches, ATSR-1 crossing
50.0 N 27th March 1996 at 11:27:15 UTC
ESA/ESTEC/NW, ERS-1, 35-day repeat orbit (501), 58.337 deg First Orbit 24574 Last Orbit 24574

ATSR FRIDAY 28 March

Western Approaches, ATSR-1 crossing
50.0 N 28th March 1996 at 22:17:50 UTC
ESA/ESTEC/NW, ERS-1, 35-day repeat orbit (501), 58.337 deg First Orbit 24595 Last Orbit 24595

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Type	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
10:36:54		T	12800	P	265	51.19	-2.39	3/8 cu Below hazy clear above.	
10:42:18		T	266	P	266	51.08	-2.99	2/8 cu below slight banding crystal clear above.	
10:47:37		T	410 377	P	272	51.05	-3.64	clear below sc to south (part) cloud appear fairly solid ahead.	
10:50:04		T	25200	P	278	51.04	-3.95	clear below sc around clear above.	
10:52:09	12	P1	28000	V	280	51.06	-4.20	clear below 3/8 cu ahead solid sc in distance.	
10:12:54		P1	4300	V	275	51.19	-6.38	solid sc cloud top. 3800 ft.	
11:16:01		P1	2700	P	85	51.14	-6.41	solid sc above: 2700 cloud base	
11:19:51		P1	500	R	83	51.17	-6.12	Broken sc 7/8 above.	
11:21:10		^{end} P1	50	R	80	51.17	-6.07	7/8 sc above 1027 sea state 5-6	
11:23:30	15	P1						Run one	
11:26:38	16	R1	2100	R	259	51.19	-6.37	abandon Run.	
11:37:48	17	P2	7500	P	192	50.81	-5.81	heading back to land end to see clouds start of profile back down to surface 200 North of Cornwall Run	
11:34:55		P2	4.7K		177	50.69	-5.43	1/8 cu Below solid sc to starboard and ahead. Aerosol 2.5 Kf/ft.	

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Phase	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
11:44:19		P2	1800	P	174	50.46	-5.92	to 1100ft across. (8)	
11:48:20	19	P2e	50	P	223	50.22	-6.08	4/8 cu above. turning to clear w/c. 1026 55-4	
11:50:11	20	R2	100	R	48	50.35	-6.14	2/8 cu above. 537	
12:02:14								Sea gull. 570 Surf.	
12:05:58								300 feet to miss sea gulls.	
12:05:47	21	R2end	100	R	44	50.88	-5.37	No cloud above.	
								Next Run to be displaced due to excessive number of sea gulls (gulls)	
12:09:46	22	R2.2	100	R	24	50.92	-5.60	less than 1/2 cu above to clear no cirrus.	
12:20:20	23	R2.2e	100	R	22	50.44	-6.14	1/8 cu above.	
12:21:31	24	R3.1	1000	R	51			Report Aerosol Field Run.	
12:33:30	25	R3.1e	1000	R	51	50.89	-5.45	Clear above, hazy below sand ^{in the} distance.	
12:34:42	26	R3.2	1000	R	227	50.89	-5.52	1/8 cu above. no ci	
12:42:04	27	R3.2	1000	R	229	50.64	-6.02	1/8 cu above - Sc ahead.	
12:46:41	27	R3.2e	1000	R	230	50.44	-6.31	3/8 - 5/8 & clear above. clear below.	

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pressure	INS leading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
12:49:22	28	P3	50	R		50.50	-7.25	1026 Sea state 4 4/8 cu.	
12:53:57		P3	2.2	P	48	50.65	-6.00	ver of hazy in broken ce layer clear above	
12:57:30	29	P3	4.0	P	50	50.77	-5.79	Change to 50 1000 ft/min $\frac{1}{8}$ cu below.	
13:03:32	30	P3.1 R4	1000	P	261	50.97	-5.61	$\frac{1}{8}$ cu below Clear above. 8 minute Run for Series.	
13:11:32	30	R4e	1000	P	265	50.89	-6.28	$\frac{7}{8}$ Sc below solid sc ahead.	
13:13:22	31	P3.2	1000	P	63	50.86	-6.26	$\frac{6}{8}$ cu 1/2 below hazy clear above.	
13:21:15								Ozone gitter pulse.	
13:23:05	32	P3.2e R5	19900	P	71	51.06	-5.40	$\frac{1}{8}$ cu below hazy clear above.	
13:31:00	34	R5 P3.3	19900	P	69	51.21	-4.65	hazy & clear Below.	
13:34:50								jet flew overhead L1011 or DC10	
13:37:01		P3.3	26.3	P	71	51.32	-4.06	hazy below clear above hazy below.	
13:41:22	35	P3.3e	300	P	96	51.25	-3.65	clear hazy below clear above 20 14'	

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: A444

Date: 27 03 96

A/S Name: TAYL

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required?
YES NO for 2 FOR HANDLE SOUTHAMPTON
2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state period
3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of Project
4. Do you want the video tape kept?
YES NO How long? 10 YRS 1 COPY
5. Has the Handheld camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished?
6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept?
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in? MRF 14: E 3
7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data TEMPORARILY until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. A444 Date: 270396 User: KATE (NERC)
Interactive by: PERCIVAL /KATE
Date: 0204 96

Renav

Vel N on
Vel E on

Pos N on
Pos E on

TWC

Profile plotted: P1
Line chosen: Profile / ~~Whole flight / Other~~

a = - 0.3542 E +1
b = + 0.4480 E -02
c = + -0.1135 E -06

LWC

OK.

Heimann / Barnes

FLIGHT LEADER'S IN-FLIGHT LOG

Date 270396 Flight No. A444

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VIDEO TAPE

No. A444 41

Ends 1350

- DFC
- RFC
- FFC

	GPS	INU
Lat.	<u>51° 09.83N</u>	<u>51° N 09.81</u>
Long.	<u>001° 44.60W</u>	<u>001° 44.63W</u>
Time	<u>0912</u>	<u>0913</u>

DRS recording to HORACE

HORACE recording to optical disk

SATCOM sending position reports

Time GMT	Event No	HT	QNH	HDG	IAS	TAS	TAT	D.P.	D.I. Htr.		
<u>091243</u>											
<u>101700</u>											
<u>102825</u>											
<u>105204</u>	<u>12</u>	<u>FL260</u>	<u>1013</u>	<u>290</u>	<u>185</u>	<u>134</u>	<u>-426</u>	<u>-54.8</u>	<u>OFF</u>		<u>1000</u>
<u>111338</u>	<u>13</u>	<u>4000</u>	<u>1013</u>	<u>270/8</u>	<u>180</u>	<u>92.3</u>	<u>-1.7</u>	<u>-11.1</u>	<u>ON</u>		<u>500/m</u>
<u>112108</u>	<u>14</u>	<u>5000</u>	<u>1027</u>	<u>090</u>	<u>180</u>	<u>88</u>	<u>3.5</u>	<u>-2.4</u>	<u>OFF</u>		<u>550/6</u>
<u>112337</u>	<u>15</u>	<u>100</u>	<u>1027</u>	<u>280</u>	<u>180</u>	<u>87.8</u>	<u>3.0</u>	<u>-3.3</u>	<u>OFF</u>		
<u>112637</u>	<u>16</u>	<u>100</u>	<u>1027</u>	<u>280</u>	<u>180</u>	<u>90</u>	<u>3.1</u>	<u>-3.2</u>	<u>OFF</u>		
<u>113747</u>	<u>17</u>	<u>FL070</u>	<u>1013</u>	<u>180</u>	<u>180</u>	<u>98</u>	<u>-3.3</u>	<u>OFF</u>	<u>OFF</u>		<u>1000/m</u>
<u>114103</u>	<u>18</u>	<u>4000</u>	<u>RAI</u>	<u>180</u>	<u>180</u>	<u>93.6</u>	<u>-4.1</u>	<u>-18.0</u>			<u>300 Ft/m</u>
<u>114815</u>	<u>19</u>	<u>50</u>	<u>1026</u>	<u>230</u>	<u>180</u>	<u>3.2</u>	<u>-3.4</u>	<u>OFF</u>	<u>OFF</u>		<u>55-6</u>

Ak
 H6
 10P
 SM
 DP
 26
 LCB
 11P
 SL
 KA
 20
 26

1730m

Video Tape ok? 1350

TIME GMT	EVENT NO	HT	QNH	HDG	IAS	TAS	TAT	D.P.	D.I. Htr.		
						START	RUN	2-1			
15011	20	100 ^{FL}	1026	055	180	90	3.0	-2.0	OFF		
						END	R2.1				
20119	21	100 ^{FL}	1026	050	185	91.7	2.2	-5.2	OFF		
						START	R2.2				
20948	22	100 ^{FL}	1026	220	180	88.2	3.0	-5.1	OFF		
						END	R2.2				
22123	23	100	1026	220	180	89			OFF		
						START	R3.1				
2215	24	1000 ^{FL}	1026	060	180	90.5	0.6	-4.2	OFF		Maximum cal 06.
						END	R3.1				
23331	25	1000 ^{FL}	1026	055	185	90.2	0.3	-5.4	OFF		
						START	R3.2				
									OFF		
23417	26	1000 ^{FL}	1026	235	185	92.1	0.5	-4.3			
						END	R3.2				
24642	27	1000 ^{FL}	1026	240	180	91.2	0.6	-3.7	OFF		
						START	P3.1	↗			500 ^{FL}
2492	28	50 ^{FL}	1026	060	180	90.2	3.4	-3.5	OFF		4
25131	29	04100 ^{FL}	1026	060	180	96	-0.4	-31.0	OFF		1000 ^{FL}
						END	IN	P3.1	↗	START	R4
303	30	FL100	1013	270	180	103	-7.4	-31.4	OFF		
						START END	R4.	START	P3.2		31.
31132	31	FL100	1013	270	180	104.9	-7.0	-34.6	OFF		
						START	P3.2	↗			
31312	32	FL100	1013	080	180	105.2	-7.0	-35.1	OFF		

FLIGHT LEADER'S IN-FLIGHT LOG

Date 270396 Flight No. A444

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VIDEO TAPE

No. A444#1
Ends 1352

- DFC
 RFC
 FFC

	GPS	INU
Lat.	N 50 52° 29	N 50 53° 13N
Long.	W 006° 13.25	W 006° 09.16
Time	13:14:54	131537

DRS recording to HORACE

HORACE recording to optical disk

SATCOM sending position reports 4/5

Time GMT	Event No	HT	QNH	HDG	IAS	TAS	TAT	D.P.	D.I. Htr.		
						END P	3.2	1/START RS			
132306	33	FL200	1013	075	120	125	-22.4	-46.7	OFF		
				END	START	RS	//	START	P3.3		
133111	34	FL200	1013	075	120	123	-29.3	-49.2	OFF		
				END	P3.3						
134122	35	FL300	1013	100	170	140	-52	-54	OFF		
				Descend	into	AREZ					
135750				LAND		Boxembe	Down				
140314				DATA		OFF					
				51°09.58N		SHUT	DOWN.				
				1°44.63W							

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: A444 Date: 270396

Page... of 2

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0428	REF +	5	0568	/		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	3075	/		Approx 3071	
	AOSS	19	4045	2.5 F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	4095	3.0 F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	0000			As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	3897	100	100	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	4003	1010			
	A/S	9	0074	/		As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	1515	487	542		
	UP2S	82	1609	293	341		
	UIRS	83	1868	-46	311		
	UP1Z	84	151	/		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	146	/		Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	2033	/		Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2731	5	4.0	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2744	5	"	As IAT	
	UIRT	89	2762	4.5	"	As IAT	
	LP1S	91	0200	19	-1570		
	LP2S	92	4095				
	LIRS	93	4095				
	LP1Z	94	4095			Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95				Approx 0146	
	LIRZ	96				Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97				As IAT	
	LP2T	98				As IAT	
	LIRT	99				As IAT	
0436	J/W	42	997			As Indicated 0000	
	NEPH	47	X				
	HYGR	58	2353	-4.5	-3.9		
	HYCC	59	716	/		696-901	
	FDEW	138	4045			DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	4095				
	DTF	10	1817	6			
	DTC	11	5		4.2		
	NDTF	23	1054	4		same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	005				
	INCT	48	4045				
	CCN	140	4045			less than 4095 if ON	
	TWCD	70	1192	/		0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	57	/		0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	0				
	O3P	106	1274			$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3RG	113	1892				
0442							

changes
to art

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
0945	FL NO	1	Hex	0444	444	A444	Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0044	0944547	/	Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0094			Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	0547			Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec	10-711			Multipxd Hkeeping
4045							
	LATC	160	Dec	0522	51°12'57.6'		Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	4076	1°18'43.2'		Longitude
0948							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height:

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0949	TWCD	70	1194	/		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	866	/		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	0057	/		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2155			2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2223	/		2180-2470	
	HTR1	75	2076	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2139	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1024			0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4089			4095	
	EV1V	170	2043				
	EV2V	171	2043				
	NPWR	172	3536				
	EVIC	173	3968				
954	EV2C	174	3968				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK Flight No: A444 Date: 270396
for auto selection

Page: 2 of 2

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1105	REF +	5	22562	/			Approx 0568
	REF -	7	3071	/			Approx 3071
	AOSS	19	1461	/ F/S O/S	TORQUE		2047 st. and level
	AOA	18	1141	/ F/S O/S	TORQUE		2047 st. and level
	RD HT	37	4095	FL20			As Indicated 0000
	PR HT	8	2925	8.0	8.0		As Altimeter
	CABP	14	4045				
	A/S	9		1293/120	120		As ASI 0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	1843	1927/632	644		
	UP2S	82	0853	140	139		
	UIRS	83	1990	-15	317		
	UP1Z	84	0145	/			Approx 0147
	UP2Z	85	0137	/			Approx 0149
	UIRZ	86	2014	/			Approx 2061
	UP1T	87	2711	6	8.6		As IAT
	UP2T	88	2775	4	4.8		As IAT
	UIRT	89	2826	2			As IAT
	LP1S	91	551	161	112		
	LP2S	92	316	39	46		
1134	LIRS	93	1962	-20	322		
	LP1Z	94	0144	/			Approx 0150
	LP2Z	95	160	/			Approx 0146
	LIRZ	96	2054	/			Approx 2050
	LP1T	97	2838	2			As IAT
	LP2T	98	2813	2	1.9		As IAT
	LIRT	99	2834	2			As IAT
	J/W	42	2130	0.7			As Indicated 0000
	NEPH	47	X				
	HYGR	58	2340	-4	-3.5		
	HYCC	59	727	/			696-901
	FDEW	138	X				DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C
	FSTA	139	X				
	DTF	10	2193				
	DTC	11	5	7			
	NDTF	23	1932		8.1		same as De-Iced
	NDTC	24	5	7			
	INCT	48	4095				
	CCN	140	4095				less than 4095 if ON
	TWCD	70	1349	/			0000-4094
	TSAM	72	1323				0640-1860 < min
	O3	100	157				
	O3P	106	2063				$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$
	O3RG	113	2006				
1154							

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
1201	FL NO	1	Hex	444	/		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	120	/		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	111			Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	20			Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
				4095			
	LATC	160	Dec	5 77	N 50° 46' 33.6"		Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	4032	W 5° 11' 2.7"		Longitude
1203							

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: 100^{ft}

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1204	TWCD	70	1313	/		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2510	/		0000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	1303	/		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2645	/		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2245	/		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	1844	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2902	/		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1023	/		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4095	/		4095	
	EV1V	170	3472				
	EV2V	171	3132				
	NPWR	172	2692				
	EVIC	173	4090				
1213	EV2C	174	4001				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOMES	COVERS	DESCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large / Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

HERCULES VIDEO TAPE LOG

FLIGHT NO. A A444

PROJECT AISR II CAL VAL

DATE 27 : 03 : 96

TAPE NO. A444 #1 USER NERC

RETENTION PERIOD 10 YRS

GMT	TAPE COUNTER	CAMERA POSITION	REMARKS
10 50	0000	FFC	TAPE STARTED TOP OF PROFILE 1
11 2337			RUN 1 START 100 FT
11 3747			PROF 2 START 4000 → 50 FT
11 5011			RUN 2.1 START 100 FT
12 0948			RUN 2.2 START 100 FT
12 2125			RUN 3.1 START 1000 FT
12 3447			RUN 3.2 START 1000 FT
12 4912			PROF 3.1 START 50 FT → FL100
13 0333			RUN 4 START FL100
13 1322			PROF 3.2 START FL100 → FL200
13 2306			RUN 5 START FL200
13 3111			PROF 3.3 START FL200 - FL300
13 50			TAPE ENDS.
13 58			LAND

OZONE ANALYZER LOG

Project: NERC

Date: 7/13/96

User: JSS/Kent Ethylene capillary column in place

Flight No: A444

Page 1 of 4

GMT	RUN #	HEIGHT	OZONE	SCALE	REMARKS (e.g. changes in pressure)
10:35:30	Transit A				adjusted pressure to 1 comb
10:36:21	" "				" " " "
10:37:14	" "				" " " "
10:37:55	" "		40 ppb		" " " "
10:38:48	" "	"	"		" " " " SF=99.2 RF=16.69
10:39:36	" "		"		" " " "
10:40:27	" "				" " " "
10:41:28	" "				" " " "
10:42:33	" "	22000'			" " " "
10:44:11	" "		55 ppb		" " " "
10:45:31	" "				" " " "
10:45:16	" "	23000'			" " " "
10:48:33	" "				" " " "
10:49:49	" "	27000'			" " " "
10:50:34	" "				" " " " SF=99.3 RF=16.76
10:51:56	" "				adjust from 1000 comb.
10:52:45	P1				" " " "
10:53:40	" "				" " " "
10:54:57	" "	23600'			" " " "
10:57:24	" "				" " " "
10:59:54	" "	18.700			" " " "

OZONE ANALYZER LOG

Project: JFR

Date: 11/31/96

User: JOS

Flight No: A444

Page 2 of 4

GMT	RUN #	HEIGHT	OZONE	SCALE	REMARKS (e.g. changes in pressure)
110005	P1	17600	74.22		adjust SP $\rightarrow$ 1000 mb SF = 99.5 CF = 18.42.
110110	"	16500	65.10		" " "
110218	"	15400	67.38		" " "
110340	"	14000	61.85		adjust P $\rightarrow$ 1014 readjust by
110630	"	10500	71.84		1060 = SP
110925	"	8000	64.45		SP = 1076
11:11:46	"	5500	64.45		SP = 1095
11:13:15	"	4100	68.68		SP = 1100
11:22:11	40P	106'			Oscillator on ozone signal.
11:24:38	P1	100'	50.13		1123 = SP
11:32:25	Transducer?	7000'	58.9		SP = 1085.
11:34:13	" "	7000'			switched off external pump SP = 809
11:35:40	" "	7000			External pump on. SP = 1081.
11:39:52	P2	4800	65.43		SP = 1100
11:46:17	P3	900	49.80		SP = 1124
11:49:00	P2 ready	100'	48.18		switched off external internal pump & opened bypass
11:50:53	P2	100'	51.43		switch inc. pump on. closed bypass.
12:00:51	P2-1	100'	53.39		SP = 1126 SF = 99.6 CF = 18.90
12:05:50	P2-2	100'	52.58		SP = 1122
12:09:30	P2-2	100'	50.08		SP = 1125.
12:18:30					all units down

OZONE ANALYZER LOG

Project: NERL

Date: 27/3/96

User: Joss

Flight No: A444

Page 3 of 4

GMT	RUN #	HEIGHT	OZONE	SCALE	REMARKS (e.g. changes in pressure)
12:20:10	R2.2	1000'	51.76		SP = 1125.
12:32:15	R2.2	1000'	54.36		SP = 1122
12:47:15	and R2.2	1000'	57.62		SP = 1126 <i>atmosphere still visible</i>
12:58:33	P3	5100'	64.72		1000mb
12:59:6	~	5800	63.8		adjust SP → 1000mb SF = 990 $\gamma = 18.41$
13:00:22	~	6800	67.29		" " " "
13:01:27	~	8000	63.80		" " " "
13:02:20	and P3.1	9100	71.61		" " " "
13:04:06	Start R3	10000'	75.19		" " " "
13:14:25	R3 P3.2	11000'	63.80		" " " "
13:16:00	~	12400	62.17		" " " "
13:17:28	~	13900	67.38		" " " "
13:18:25	~	15000	67.71		" " " "
13:19:18	~	15900	79.1		" " " "
13:20:50	~	17900	70.31		" " " " SF = 99.4 $\gamma = 17.22$
13:21:40	~	18600	72.92		" " " "
13:22:00	~	19800	81.38		" " " "
13:25:00	R4	19900	77.47		" " " "
13:31:50	R3.5	20800	63.80		" " " "
13:32:47	R3.3	22000	72.17		" " " "
13:33:50	~	23000	63.12		" " " "

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. A444

Date: 27/3/96

Operator: MP

Page 2 of 2

G.M.T.		PCASP		FSSP			2D-C			HVPS / 2D-P			REMARKS
DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Conc/cc	Max Size	Reff	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m ³	Max Size	Habit		
114010	90	0.09										5000'	
114053	170	0.10										4000'	
114216	230	0.11	0.4	5								3000'	
114358	305	0.13	0.2	15								2000'	
114542	287	0.12	0.4	10								1000'	
114710	440	0.11	0.2	5								500'	
114818	440	0.11	0.4	5								end of Run @ 50'	
115010												Start Run 2 @ 100'	
115100	380	0.11	0.6	10									
115300	270	0.12	0.2	10									
115500	290	0.12	0.4	5									
115700	250	0.12	0.2	10									
115900	170	0.11	0.4	10									
120100	335	0.11	0.2	10									
120300	240	0.11	0.4	10									
120500	200	0.10	0.4	10									
120547													
120947													
121000	800	0.11	0.2	10								end of Run	
121000	140	0.12	0.7	10								Start Run 2 @ 100'	
121400	160	0.11	0.4	10									
121600	160	0.11	0.2	10									
121800	135	0.12	0.4	10									
122000	240	0.12	0.4	5									
122025													
122130													
122800	240	0.12	0.2	15								end of Run	
122800	215	0.12	0.05	5								Start Run 3.1 @ 1000'	
122800	200	0.12	0.2	5									
122800	225	0.11	0.2	5									
123000	210	0.11	0.4	5									
123200	220	0.11	0.4	5									
123332													
123446													
123500	160	0.11	0.2	5								end of Run	
123700	190	0.11	0.4	5								Start Run 3.2 @ 1000'	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. *ALL 4*

Date: *27/3 F16*

Operator: *MP*

Page *3* of 4

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C			HVPS / 2D-P			REMARKS
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Conc/cc	Max Size	Reff	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m ³	Max Size	Habit	
<i>123500</i>	<i>215</i>	<i>0.11</i>	<i>0.4</i>	<i>5</i>								
<i>124100</i>	<i>180</i>	<i>0.11</i>	<i>0.2</i>	<i>5</i>								
<i>124300</i>	<i>140</i>	<i>0.11</i>	<i>0.7</i>	<i>5</i>								
<i>124500</i>	<i>190</i>	<i>0.11</i>	<i>0.3</i>	<i>5</i>								
<i>124640</i>												
<i>124912</i>	<i>280</i>	<i>0.12</i>	<i>0.2</i>	<i>10</i>								<i>end of Run</i>
<i>125122</i>	<i>210</i>	<i>0.12</i>	<i>0.4</i>	<i>10</i>								<i>Start PG Run 50'</i>
<i>125308</i>	<i>165</i>	<i>0.12</i>	<i>0.6</i>	<i>10</i>								<i>1000'</i>
<i>125447</i>	<i>170</i>	<i>0.12</i>	<i>1.1</i>	<i>15</i>								<i>2000'</i>
<i>125444</i>	<i>70</i>	<i>0.09</i>										<i>3000'</i>
<i>125827</i>	<i>48</i>	<i>0.09</i>										<i>4000</i>
<i>125933</i>	<i>40</i>	<i>0.09</i>										<i>5000'</i>
<i>130041</i>	<i>25</i>	<i>0.09</i>										<i>6000'</i>
<i>130131</i>	<i>16</i>	<i>0.09</i>										<i>7000'</i>
<i>130222</i>	<i>22</i>	<i>0.09</i>										<i>8000'</i>
<i>130332</i>	<i>22</i>	<i>0.09</i>										<i>9000'</i>
<i>130400</i>	<i>35</i>	<i>0.09</i>										<i>FL100 & Start Run 4</i>
<i>130600</i>	<i>39</i>	<i>0.09</i>										FL100
<i>130800</i>	<i>45</i>	<i>0.09</i>										
<i>131000</i>	<i>35</i>	<i>0.09</i>										
<i>131132</i>												
<i>131322</i>												<i>end of Run</i>
<i>131462</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>0.07</i>										<i>Cont P</i>
<i>131535</i>	<i>11</i>	<i>0.09</i>										<i>FL110</i>
<i>131637</i>	<i>15</i>	<i>0.08</i>										<i>FL120</i>
<i>131737</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>0.08</i>										<i>FL130</i>
<i>131847</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>0.09</i>										<i>FL140</i>
<i>131933</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>0.09</i>										<i>FL150</i>
<i>132015</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>0.09</i>										<i>FL160</i>
<i>132119</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>0.09</i>										<i>FL170</i>
<i>132213</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>0.09</i>										<i>FL180</i>
<i>132308</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>0.09</i>										<i>FL190</i>
<i>132600</i>	<i>7</i>	<i>0.09</i>										<i>FL200</i>
<i>133000</i>	<i>8</i>	<i>0.09</i>										
<i>133110</i>												
<i>133210</i>												<i>end of Run & Start P</i>

DATE 27 MAR TI MRF NAVY 801 NAV 4444
 AIRFIELD BOSCOMBE C AIRFIELD _____
 R/W OS W/V 08/15 TEMP 2 ONH 1025 OFF 1010 R/W OS W/V 090/11 TEMP +6 ONH 1025 OFF 1010
 WX 4/3500 LSM WX BLUF
 ATC CL R ATC CL 2500

T/O TIME S 3310 S4, 1030 LAND TIME 1400 3:30

TIME	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT/LONG	RUN
1052 ⁰¹	280	3P	297	190	270	051/35	F260		N51019 W04123	P1
1121 ⁰²						090/20	4000 ^{50'}	1027	N51080 W06053	
1121 ⁰²							50		N51080 W06	
23 ³⁷	271	?	?	178	175	076/20	1000		N51006 W06058	R1
23 ³⁷									N51116 W06197	
37 ⁴⁷	189	3S	199	183	200	091/08	F070		N50486 W05534	P2
42 ⁵⁰						095/11	50'		N50190 W06053	
50 ⁰⁰	046	4P	158	180	178	108/14	100		N50205 W06091	R2
1205 ⁴⁹									N50534 N05212	
09 ⁴⁹	214	6S	175	176	173	070/14	100		N50359 W05355	R2
20 ²³									N50301 W06077	
21 ²⁵	05	2P	177	185	184	093/17	1000		N50290 W06059	R3
									N50529 W05269	
24 ⁴⁷	205	3S	192	192	181	087/18	1000		N50538 W05303	R3
46 ⁰²							100		N50298 W06182	
1249 ⁴²	050	1P	173	181	187	092/11	50'	1020	N50292 W06163	P3
1305 ³³	254	2P	213	207	180	020/7	1000 ¹⁰⁰⁰	1100	N49380 W06180	R4
11 ³²									N50534 W06175	
1322	061	1S	204	180	210	039/8	F100		N50510 W06165	P3
23 ⁰⁰	089	3S	239	184	250	034/16	F200		N51035 W05263	R5
31 ⁰⁰	070	3S	240	178	245	042/14			N51123 W04401	R2
									N51123 W04401	R3
44 ²²							F300		N51150 W03385	

INSTRUMENT STATUS AND REQUIREMENT FORM
A444 27MAR96 MRFATS - New

STANDARD INSTRUMENTS			
EXP PIT STAT HEAD			
Pitot-static	On	Des	
Wind Vanes	On	Des	
THERMOMETERS			
ICTP	On	Ess	OFFLINE
De-iced	On	Ess	
Non De-iced	On	Ess	
HYGROMETERS			
Gen East (1011)	On	Ess	
Fluor W V S	X		
AEROSOL SAMPLING			
Filters	X		
CN Counter	X		
VACC	X		
PSAP	X		
CVI	X		
Alleviator	On		
CCN	X		
Nephelometer	X		
CHEMICAL			
TECO Ozone	X		
Bendix Ozone (eth)	On	Des	
ECGC's	X		
UEA Peroxide	X		
KFA	X		
IMAGERY			
Weather Radar	X		
Video Cameras	On	Ess	
Video Rec	On	Ess	
Photo Cameras	On	Des	
Hand Held Video	On	Des	
DATA RECORDING			
Video printer	On	Ess	
Horace	On	Ess	
DRS	On	Ess	

NAVIGATION/AIRCRAFT PERFORMANCE			
INS	On	Ess	
GPS	On	Ess	
Mag compass	On	Ess	
Omega	On	Ess	
radar Alt	On	Ess	
CLOUD PHYSICS			
PCASP	On	Ess	
2D CLOUD	X	Des	****
FSSP	On	Des	
HVPS	X		
JW	On	Ess	
Tot Water	X	Des	****
DROPSONDE SYSTEM			
Sondes	On		
Receivers	On		
RADIOMETERS			
Deimos	On	Des	
Heimann	On	Ess	
BROAD BAND LOWER			
Standard Fit	On	Ess	
Non standard	X		
BROAD BAND UPPER			
Standard fit	On	Ess	
Non standard	X		
Obscurers (L)	X		
Obscurers (S)	On	Ess	
NARROW BAND			
Marss	On	Des	
MCR/SAFIRE	X		

R : Remove, C : Cover
T/O TIME - 10:30 local

① ~~Upper~~ Clear BBR. descricant needs changing.

② Horace locked up when in IAN display page at 0912.
No action when press "C-INUMEN" or any other key
all displays Jam. Chr 'w' no good. Reset graphics boxes.

Mess on reset has BOOT STRAP FAILURE
DEV OFF LINE DUAD
HLT INST
PC = 01000D42.

Switched off and restarted 0920

~~③ FSS? (switch) pre fbb.~~

③ Low BBR zero pre takeoff - reset but no good. Come on 21040.

④ SATCOM. Unable to send.
Can't submit - unable to find message 00040 ----
Unable to send any message.

⑤ Hand Held video batteries U15. Need recharging.

A444

GPS data
08:14:55 - 14:03:05

ASXX EGRR MSLP ANALYSIS DT 0000 UTC 27 MAR 1996

Polar Stereographic Projection. Standard Parallel 60°N. Original scale 1:20m

PHSE.001
FROM MET IT OPS BRACKNELL TO 4806
27 MAR '96 03:23

**GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR 4 MB INTERVALS**

SCALE OF NAUTICAL MILES

00Z WED 27/ 3/96 V1 00Z WED 27/ 3/96 GMAIN T+ 0

HEIGHT DM. 500MB

300-1000MB 500MB

MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_2 PAGE. 701

27 MAR '96 04:22

PLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03.37.39

CHART 13

PHEA50 EGRR 0000Z

ASXX EGRR MSLP ANALYSIS DT 1200 UTC 27 MAR 1996

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE FAX F: ***

Pole/Stereographic Projection. Standard Parallel 60°N. Original scale 1:20m

PAGE.001

TO 4806

FROM MET IT OPS BRACKNELL

27 MAR '96 15:37

Prepared and drawn on the Cartographic Section, Met.O. J.S. ...

27 MAR '96 15:37

*** TOTAL PAGE.001 ***

ASAX EGRR MSLP ANALYSIS L 0600 UTC 2 MAR 96

Polar Stereographic Projection. Standard Parallel 60°N. Origin: scale 1:20m

27 MAR '96 09:48 FROM MET IT OPS BRACKNELL TO 4806

** TOTAL PAGE 001 **
The Met Office PAGE 00

MOD '96 18:14

HDG deg T 265.	SPR mb 697.	PHGT k.ft 10.0	TAS knots 209.	TAT C -7.1	DEW C -34.5	WIND deg m/s 023/5
----------------------	-------------------	----------------------	----------------------	------------------	-------------------	--------------------------

A444 27 MARCH 96 13:07:15 030.0 50.92

-57

FRP

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	DEVICE	FREQ	ZOOM			MODE	HELP

HDS degT 265.	SAR mb 696.	PHGT kft 10.0	TAS knots 209.	TAT C -7.0	DEW C -34.4	WIND deg m/s 023/ 4
---------------------	-------------------	---------------------	----------------------	------------------	-------------------	---------------------------

A444 27-MAR-96 13:10:18 030.2 50.90 -6.18 FRP

A SELECT	B PARAS	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
-------------	------------	-----------	-----------	---	---	------------	-----------

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
64.	679.	10.7	213.	-8.4	-32.2	047 / 5

15.00 15.00
 12.50 12.50
 10.00 10.00
 7.50 7.50
 5.00 5.00
 2.50 2.50
 0.00 0.00

A444 27-MAR-96 13:14:03 032.0 50.87 -6.22 FR P

A SELECT	B PARAM	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
-------------	------------	-----------	-----------	---	---	------------	-----------

HGT degT	QPR mb	QHT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
64.	646.	11.9	218.	-11.1	-30.9	042/ 5

A444
27-MAR-96
13:15:30
032 N
50.92
-6.12
FRP

A SELECT	B PARAS	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
-------------	------------	-----------	-----------	---	---	------------	-----------

HDG deg T 68.	SPR mb 589.	PHGT kft 14.3	TAS knots 229.	TAT C -16.9	DEW C -30.9	WIND deg m/s 016/4
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A444 27 MAR 96 13:17:57 032 Ω 50.97 -5.91 FR P

A SELECT	B PARAS	C FREQ	D ZOOM	E	F	G VIDEO	H HELP
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LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
1 1 1 1	Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log
1d/2 2d/2 2 1	Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight log Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)
0 0 0 0 4+1	SAFIRE log CCN log MARSS log DEIMOS log Chemistry log
0 4 0 1 0	Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)
1 - - - - -	Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track

A445 28-MAR-96 11:10:00-14:15:00GMT

mercator projection

INS TRACK - run no

A445 28-MAR-96 Height time series

A444 Profile 1

| Non Deiced True Temp

| Dew Point (GE)

| Dew Point (TW)

A444 Profile2

| Non Deiced True Temp

| Dew Point (GE)

| Dew Point (TW)

A444 Profile3

Non Deiced True Temp

Dew Point (GE)

Dew Point (TW)

Meteosat-IR 270396 1100GMT

ANHRR
27 MARCH 1996
11:50 AM

AVHR

27 MARCH 1996

13:29

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 9901
Mean 50.8522
Standard dev 0.253485
Max value 51.2733
Min value 50.2784

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 9901
Mean -5.76971
Standard dev 0.503145
Max value -3.92233
Min value -6.51309

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735
No. of obs 9901
Mean 2.88095
Standard dev 56.9325
Max value 99.5603
Min value -137.536

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 9901
Mean -2.75655
Standard dev 86.9931
Max value 123.154
Min value -154.133

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 9901
Mean 271.634
Standard dev 11.1439
Max value 281.157
Min value 236.284

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 9901
Mean 266.500
Standard dev 12.3771
Max value 277.091
Min value 228.622

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 9901
Mean 271.520
Standard dev 11.1615
Max value 281.083
Min value 236.131

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 9901
Mean 266.236
Standard dev 12.4301
Max value 276.908
Min value 228.247

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 9901
Mean 277.396
Standard dev 11.5955
Max value 281.715
Min value 0.000000

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 9901
Mean 1.52261
Standard dev 1.23839
Max value 3.33990
Min value 0.000000

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 9901
Mean 243.346
Standard dev 56.8957
Max value 274.828
Min value 0.000000

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 9901
Mean 236.646
Standard dev 62.7741
Max value 271.754
Min value 0.000000

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 9901
Mean 0.469937
Standard dev 3.618436e-02
Max value 0.844657
Min value 0.370706

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 9901
Mean 830.994
Standard dev 210.538
Max value 1026.70
Min value 361.222

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 9901
Mean 56.1904
Standard dev 7.54482
Max value 100.413
Min value 43.2285

1 second overages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 9901
Mean 1898.08
Standard dev 2345.90
Max value 7899.05
Min value -111.371

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 9901
Mean 615.636
Standard dev 643.149
Max value 1522.15
Min value 0.000000

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 9901
Mean 6.89276
Standard dev 1.79235
Max value 12.3689
Min value 0.605950

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 9901
Mean 744.121
Standard dev 150.453
Max value 1100.05
Min value 205.542

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 9901
Mean 374.686
Standard dev 85.1101
Max value 579.904
Min value 85.0850

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 9901
Mean 991.158
Standard dev 28.9410
Max value 1049.50
Min value 940.759

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

UPP VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 679
No. of obs 9901
Mean 273.828
Standard dev 10.5243
Max value 282.249
Min value 242.747

UPP VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 680
No. of obs 9901
Mean 272.126
Standard dev 10.9408
Max value 280.847
Min value 240.048

UPP I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 681
No. of obs 9901
Mean 271.792
Standard dev 11.0179
Max value 280.464
Min value 239.297

10:50:00 11:31:15 12:12:30 12:53:45 13:35:00

TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

LWR VIS CLR SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 682
No. of obs 9901
Mean 142.607
Standard dev 95.8164
Max value 597.984
Min value 66.5323

LWR VIS RED SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 683
No. of obs 9901
Mean 68.0023
Standard dev 47.9909
Max value 287.674
Min value 29.1509

LWR I/R SIGNAL (WM-2)

Parameter no. 684
No. of obs 9901
Mean 505.549
Standard dev 27.9994
Max value 588.072
Min value 446.594

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

LWR VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 688
No. of obs 9901
Mean 271.567
Standard dev 10.9394
Max value 280.161
Min value 239.392

LWR VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 689
No. of obs 9901
Mean 272.656
Standard dev 11.2072
Max value 281.417
Min value 239.646

LWR I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 690
No. of obs 9901
Mean 271.897
Standard dev 11.1959
Max value 280.494
Min value 238.532

10:50:00 11:31:15 12:12:30 12:53:45 13:35:00
TIME (GMT)

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 9901
Mean 148.727
Standard dev 126.381
Max value 764.322
Min value 1.00000

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 9901
Mean 0.104636
Standard dev 3.591762e-02
Max value 0.767634
Min value 5.475000e-02

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 9901
Mean 6.64223
Standard dev 28.6109
Max value 480.913
Min value 6.873999e-04

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R_all

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 9901
Mean 0.149817
Standard dev 8.344162e-02
Max value 1.01615
Min value 5.475782e-02

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 9901
Mean 0.121621
Standard dev 5.663022e-02
Max value 0.930934
Min value 5.475257e-02

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 9901
Mean 0.244058
Standard dev 0.202788
Max value 1.34557
Min value 5.474088e-02

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

10:50:00 11:31:15 12:12:30 12:53:45 13:35:00
TIME (GMT)

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P1

Times 10:52:09-11:21:08 GMT

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P1

Times 10:52:09-11:21:08 GMT

1 second averages

TW

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P1

Times 10:52:09-11:21:08 GMT

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P1

Times 10:52:09-11:21:08 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S⁻¹)

Parameter no. 736

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P1

Times 10:52:09-11:21:08 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

225 255 285
NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)
Parameter no. 524

225 255 285
NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
Parameter no. 525

205 245 285
SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
Parameter no. 537

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P1

Times 10:52:09-11:21:08 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P1

Times 10:52:09-11:21:08 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P1

Times 10:52:09-11:21:08 GMT

J/W LWC (G KG-1)
Parameter no. 535

1 second averages

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)
Parameter no. 577

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
Parameter no. 574

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P1

Times 10:52:09-11:21:08 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P1

Times 10:52:09-11:21:08 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

0.0 0.5 1.0
PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)
Parameter no. 922

0.0 0.5 1.0
PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)
Parameter no. 923

0.00 0.75 1.50
PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)
Parameter no. 924

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P2

Times 11:37:47-11:48:15 GMT

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P2

Times 11:37:47-11:48:15 GMT

1 second averages

TW

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P2

Times 11:37:47-11:48:15 GMT

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P2

Times 11:37:47-11:48:15 GMT

Parameter no. 730

1 second averages

Parameter no. 731

Parameter no. 735

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P2

Times 11:37:47-11:48:15 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P2

Times 11:37:47-11:48:15 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

225 255 285
NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)
Parameter no. 524

225 255 285
NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
Parameter no. 525

205 245 285
SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
Parameter no. 537

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P2

Times 11:37:47-11:48:15 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P2

Times 11:37:47-11:48:15 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P2

Times 11:37:47-11:48:15 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P2

Times 11:37:47-11:48:15 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P3

Times 12:49:12-13:41:22 GMT

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P3

Times 12:49:12-13:41:22 GMT

1 second averages

TW

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P3

Times 12:49:12-13:41:22 GMT

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P3

Times 12:49:12-13:41:22 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P3

Times 12:49:12-13:41:22 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P3

Times 12:49:12-13:41:22 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

225 255 285
NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)
Parameter no. 524

225 255 285
NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
Parameter no. 525

205 245 285
SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)
Parameter no. 537

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P3

Times 12:49:12-13:41:22 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)
Parameter no. 572

DEW POINT (DEG K)
Parameter no. 529

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)
Parameter no. 725

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P3

Times 12:49:12-13:41:22 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P3

Times 12:49:12-13:41:22 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96 Profile P3

Times 12:49:12-13:41:22 GMT

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

0.0 0.5 1.0
PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)
Parameter no. 922

0.0 0.5 1.0
PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)
Parameter no. 923

0.00 0.75 1.50
PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)
Parameter no. 924

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R1

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 181
Mean 80.8892
Standard dev 6.01429
Max value 94.5507
Min value 65.0769

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 181
Mean 10.6278
Standard dev 0.723699
Max value 13.7203
Min value 8.63072

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 181
Mean north -1.67403
Stan dev north 1.10023
Max north 0.862202
Min north -4.40105
Mean east -1.67403
Stan dev east 1.10023
Max east 0.862202
Min east -4.40105

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R1

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 181
Mean 51.1799
Standard dev 2.551537e-03
Max value 51.1849
Min value 51.1760

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 181
Mean -6.22285
Standard dev 7.670292e-02
Max value -6.09177
Min value -6.35545

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735
No. of obs 181
Mean 5.47845
Standard dev 1.74644
Max value 8.65937
Min value 1.34514

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R1

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 181
Mean -102.031
Standard dev 2.06701
Max value -95.8592
Min value -105.613

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 181
Mean 280.366
Standard dev 0.363418
Max value 281.157
Min value 279.238

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 181
Mean 276.359
Standard dev 0.239480
Max value 276.910
Min value 275.657

11:23:37 11:24:22 11:25:07 11:25:52 11:26:37
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R1

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 181
Mean 280.266
Standard dev 0.374724
Max value 281.083
Min value 279.092

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 181
Mean 276.142
Standard dev 0.246027
Max value 276.710
Min value 275.411

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 181
Mean 280.975
Standard dev 0.340609
Max value 281.379
Min value 280.335

11:23:37 11:24:22 11:25:07 11:25:52 11:26:37

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R1

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 181
Mean 2.78228
Standard dev 0.110750
Max value 3.11795
Min value 2.56498

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 181
Mean 269.631
Standard dev 0.494742
Max value 271.248
Min value 268.853

DEW POINT (DEG K)

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 181
Mean 269.233
Standard dev 0.534832
Max value 270.786
Min value 268.113

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

11:23:37 11:24:22 11:25:07 11:25:52 11:26:37
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R1

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 181
Mean 0.441632
Standard dev 1.169814e-02
Max value 0.479856
Min value 0.389931

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 181
Mean 1023.41
Standard dev 2.07480
Max value 1024.77
Min value 1015.70

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 181
Mean 55.3539
Standard dev 2.80033
Max value 60.8029
Min value 48.1705

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R1

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 181
Mean -84.2236
Standard dev 17.1686
Max value -20.4093
Min value -95.4482

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 181
Mean 37.7859
Standard dev 16.5606
Max value 99.8224
Min value 27.3401

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 181
Mean 9.38544
Standard dev 0.220873
Max value 9.84189
Min value 8.90694

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R1

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 181
Mean 515.741
Standard dev 222.967
Max value 1006.27
Min value 0.000000

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 181
Mean 250.527
Standard dev 113.624
Max value 509.626
Min value 0.000000

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 181
Mean 961.716
Standard dev 289.905
Max value 1049.50
Min value 0.000000

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R1

UPP VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 679
No. of obs 181
Mean 281.075
Standard dev 0.183491
Max value 281.298
Min value 280.618

UPP VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 680
No. of obs 181
Mean 279.538
Standard dev 0.211981
Max value 279.814
Min value 279.016

UPP I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 681
No. of obs 181
Mean 279.489
Standard dev 0.245734
Max value 279.760
Min value 278.915

11:23:37 11:24:22 11:25:07 11:25:52 11:26:37
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R1

LWR VIS CLR SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 682
No. of obs 181
Mean 81.6298
Standard dev 8.99778
Max value 99.1936
Min value 71.3710

LWR VIS RED SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 683
No. of obs 181
Mean 40.6282
Standard dev 3.24059
Max value 48.0735
Min value 36.8222

LWR I/R SIGNAL (WM-2)

Parameter no. 684
No. of obs 181
Mean 494.910
Standard dev 1.64196
Max value 497.730
Min value 491.643

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R1

LWR VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 688
No. of obs 181
Mean 279.412
Standard dev 0.205480
Max value 279.753
Min value 279.026

LWR VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 689
No. of obs 181
Mean 280.634
Standard dev 0.200484
Max value 280.982
Min value 280.209

LWR I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 690
No. of obs 181
Mean 280.083
Standard dev 0.158734
Max value 280.402
Min value 279.758

11:23:37 11:24:22 11:25:07 11:25:52 11:26:37
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R1

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 181
Mean 401.091
Standard dev 57.0567
Max value 590.104
Min value 138.220

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 181
Mean 0.107420
Standard dev 4.496887e-03
Max value 0.122592
Min value 9.689796e-02

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 181
Mean 5.45466
Standard dev 3.30611
Max value 17.9191
Min value 1.77639

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R1

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 181
Mean 0.143656
Standard dev 2.683073e-02
Max value 0.226293
Min value 0.109492

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 181
Mean 0.118794
Standard dev 9.003704e-03
Max value 0.154349
Min value 0.103364

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 181
Mean 0.218576
Standard dev 9.700777e-02
Max value 0.594311
Min value 0.117692

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

11:23:37 11:24:22 11:25:07 11:25:52 11:26:37
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.1

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 939
Mean 93.2772
Standard dev 7.76563
Max value 113.632
Min value 73.0294

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 939
Mean 7.75679
Standard dev 1.05426
Max value 10.8589
Min value 4.77251

WIND COMP (METRES/S)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 939
Mean north 0.451586
Stan dev north 1.04743
Max north 3.12300
Min north -2.05661
Mean east 0.451586
Stan dev east 1.04743
Max east 3.12300
Min east -2.05661

1 second averages

11:50:11 11:54:05 11:58:00 12:01:54 12:05:49

TIME (GMT)

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.1

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 939
Mean 50.5951
Standard dev 0.160254
Max value 50.8718
Min value 50.3217

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 939
Mean -5.76154
Standard dev 0.228123
Max value -5.36718
Min value -6.15316

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735
No. of obs 939
Mean 65.1700
Standard dev 2.05883
Max value 67.8837
Min value 50.4614

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.1

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 939
Mean 59.1093
Standard dev 1.41255
Max value 65.8654
Min value 55.3966

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 939
Mean 280.282
Standard dev 0.189629
Max value 280.919
Min value 279.223

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 939
Mean 276.178
Standard dev 0.166137
Max value 276.726
Min value 275.505

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.1

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 939
Mean 280.179
Standard dev 0.196074
Max value 280.840
Min value 279.078

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 939
Mean 275.954
Standard dev 0.171497
Max value 276.522
Min value 275.252

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 939
Mean 280.950
Standard dev 0.258104
Max value 281.642
Min value 280.414

11:50:11 11:54:05 11:58:00 12:01:54 12:05:49

TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.1

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 939
Mean 2.61411
Standard dev 0.108518
Max value 3.07966
Min value 2.37211

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 939
Mean 269.016
Standard dev 0.610168
Max value 271.360
Min value 267.468

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 939
Mean 268.394
Standard dev 0.547547
Max value 270.605
Min value 267.131

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

11:50:11

11:54:05

11:58:00

12:01:54

12:05:49

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.1

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 939
Mean 0.447115
Standard dev 8.243646e-03
Max value 0.470223
Min value 0.398861

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 939
Mean 1022.93
Standard dev 0.938922
Max value 1023.75
Min value 1015.74

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 939
Mean 56.7408
Standard dev 2.02286
Max value 62.0915
Min value 50.7258

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.1

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 939
Mean -80.2422
Standard dev 7.77249
Max value -20.7462
Min value -87.0144

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 939
Mean 32.9959
Standard dev 7.65207
Max value 91.6449
Min value 27.1543

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 939
Mean 8.38627
Standard dev 0.186404
Max value 8.90848
Min value 7.76555

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.1

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 939
Mean 746.713
Standard dev 135.845
Max value 964.552
Min value 0.000000

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 939
Mean 378.035
Standard dev 75.7391
Max value 494.377
Min value 0.000000

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 939
Mean 982.809
Standard dev 156.022
Max value 1047.85
Min value 0.000000

11:50:11 11:54:05 11:58:00 12:01:54 12:05:49
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.1

UPP VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 679
No. of obs 939
Mean 281.751
Standard dev 0.200586
Max value 281.977
Min value 281.071

UPP VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 680
No. of obs 939
Mean 280.441
Standard dev 0.289473
Max value 280.753
Min value 279.486

UPP I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 681
No. of obs 939
Mean 280.186
Standard dev 0.269032
Max value 280.464
Min value 279.243

1 second averages

11:50:11 11:54:05 11:58:00 12:01:54 12:05:49
TIME (GMT)

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.1

LWR VIS CLR SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 682
No. of obs 939
Mean 89.1589
Standard dev 5.22844
Max value 105.645
Min value 70.9677

LWR VIS RED SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 683
No. of obs 939
Mean 44.4663
Standard dev 2.71720
Max value 52.6763
Min value 35.2880

LWR I/R SIGNAL (WM-2)

Parameter no. 684
No. of obs 939
Mean 494.896
Standard dev 1.67554
Max value 500.896
Min value 488.964

11:50:11 11:54:05 11:58:00 12:01:54 12:05:49
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.1

LWR VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 688
No. of obs 939
Mean 279.821
Standard dev 0.174808
Max value 280.071
Min value 279.117

LWR VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 689
No. of obs 939
Mean 281.113
Standard dev 0.206337
Max value 281.368
Min value 280.306

LWR I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 690
No. of obs 939
Mean 280.316
Standard dev 0.136197
Max value 280.494
Min value 279.666

1 second averages

11:50:11 11:54:05 11:58:00 12:01:54 12:05:49
TIME (GMT)

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.1

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 939
Mean 254.501
Standard dev 67.5204
Max value 540.249
Min value 113.147

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 939
Mean 0.112451
Standard dev 7.104172e-03
Max value 0.136523
Min value 9.532061e-02

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 939
Mean 6.65931
Standard dev 5.03057
Max value 31.4868
Min value 0.979823

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.1

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 939
Mean 0.175399
Standard dev 4.350606e-02
Max value 0.344740
Min value 0.106652

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 939
Mean 0.133071
Standard dev 1.651299e-02
Max value 0.209950
Min value 0.100843

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 939
Mean 0.320863
Standard dev 0.163843
Max value 0.940927
Min value 0.115218

1 second averages

11:50:11 11:54:05 11:58:00 12:01:54 12:05:49
TIME (GMT)

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.2

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 636
Mean 80.0503
Standard dev 7.06170
Max value 98.7503
Min value 60.8103

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 636
Mean 7.87544
Standard dev 0.821921
Max value 10.5477
Min value 5.83288

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 636
Mean north -1.33097
Stan dev north 0.926855
Max north 1.07713
Min north -3.52702
Mean east -1.33097
Stan dev east 0.926855
Max east 1.07713
Min east -3.52702

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.2

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 636
Mean 50.7083
Standard dev 0.125472
Max value 50.9243
Min value 50.4899

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 636
Mean -5.87343
Standard dev 0.159110
Max value -5.60121
Min value -6.14687

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735
No. of obs 636
Mean -76.0103
Standard dev 1.15402
Max value -73.8785
Min value -78.9120

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.2

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 636
Mean -60.4784
Standard dev 1.44608
Max value -57.4493
Min value -64.2333

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 636
Mean 280.236
Standard dev 0.173551
Max value 280.812
Min value 279.792

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 636
Mean 276.271
Standard dev 0.109969
Max value 276.716
Min value 276.039

12:09:48 12:12:26 12:15:05 12:17:44 12:20:23
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.2

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 636
Mean 280.136
Standard dev 0.177854
Max value 280.731
Min value 279.682

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 636
Mean 276.054
Standard dev 0.114047
Max value 276.514
Min value 275.833

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 636
Mean 280.868
Standard dev 0.227398
Max value 281.306
Min value 280.213

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.2

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 636
Mean 2.61171
Standard dev 0.119491
Max value 2.98554
Min value 2.25509

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 636
Mean 269.049
Standard dev 0.702119
Max value 270.949
Min value 266.995

DEW POINT (DEG K)

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 636
Mean 268.382
Standard dev 0.603273
Max value 270.169
Min value 266.466

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

12:09:48 12:12:26 12:15:05 12:17:44 12:20:23
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.2

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 636
Mean 0.445471
Standard dev 8.709133e-03
Max value 0.468109
Min value 0.417725

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 636
Mean 1023.13
Standard dev 0.357296
Max value 1024.05
Min value 1022.20

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 636
Mean 54.7780
Standard dev 1.61735
Max value 58.4010
Min value 49.2537

12:09:48 12:12:26 12:15:05 12:17:44 12:20:23

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.2

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 636
Mean -81.9349
Standard dev 2.95104
Max value -74.2082
Min value -89.4901

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 636
Mean 32.2766
Standard dev 2.05488
Max value 38.4913
Min value 26.7826

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 636
Mean 8.22346
Standard dev 0.204825
Max value 8.71426
Min value 7.62484

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.2

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 636
Mean 733.651
Standard dev 63.9122
Max value 835.180
Min value 355.583

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 636
Mean 330.912
Standard dev 32.6834
Max value 380.783
Min value 133.042

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 636
Mean 1006.56
Standard dev 2.81122
Max value 1017.10
Min value 1002.82

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.2

UPP VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 679
No. of obs 636
Mean 282.030
Standard dev 0.192188
Max value 282.249
Min value 281.433

UPP VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 680
No. of obs 636
Mean 280.596
Standard dev 0.196136
Max value 280.800
Min value 280.002

UPP I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 681
No. of obs 636
Mean 280.245
Standard dev 0.230303
Max value 280.464
Min value 279.572

12:09:48 12:12:26 12:15:05 12:17:44 12:20:23
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.2

LWR VIS CLR SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 682
No. of obs 636
Mean 95.0523
Standard dev 3.17095
Max value 102.016
Min value 77.8226

LWR VIS RED SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 683
No. of obs 636
Mean 47.3731
Standard dev 1.47488
Max value 50.3749
Min value 39.3793

LWR I/R SIGNAL (WM-2)

Parameter no. 684
No. of obs 636
Mean 495.832
Standard dev 0.783508
Max value 498.948
Min value 494.078

12:09:48 12:12:26 12:15:05 12:17:44 12:20:23
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.2

LWR VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 688
No. of obs 636
Mean 279.888
Standard dev 0.233602
Max value 280.161
Min value 279.208

LWR VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 689
No. of obs 636
Mean 281.127
Standard dev 0.231106
Max value 281.368
Min value 280.451

LWR I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 690
No. of obs 636
Mean 280.271
Standard dev 0.240444
Max value 280.494
Min value 279.528

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.2

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 636
Mean 164.695
Standard dev 37.9332
Max value 345.426
Min value 99.1095

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 636
Mean 0.111768
Standard dev 8.139286e-03
Max value 0.149137
Min value 9.388161e-02

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 636
Mean 6.14221
Standard dev 5.18352
Max value 34.0833
Min value 0.570432

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R2.2

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 636
Mean 0.193369
Standard dev 5.599504e-02
Max value 0.377693
Min value 0.107026

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 636
Mean 0.139889
Standard dev 2.365092e-02
Max value 0.240450
Min value 0.101141

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 636
Mean 0.388692
Standard dev 0.204960
Max value 0.985549
Min value 0.117246

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

12:09:48 12:12:26 12:15:05 12:17:44 12:20:23
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.1

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 727
Mean 95.9468
Standard dev 4.62208
Max value 109.086
Min value 79.4223

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 727
Mean 8.84077
Standard dev 0.754982
Max value 11.0917
Min value 6.66924

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 727
Mean north 0.909234
Stan dev north 0.703499
Max north 3.39036
Min north -1.47073
Mean east 0.909234
Stan dev east 0.703499
Max east 3.39036
Min east -1.47073

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.1

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 727
Mean 50.6644
Standard dev 0.115404
Max value 50.8623
Min value 50.4666

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 727
Mean -5.80099
Standard dev 0.183599
Max value -5.48185
Min value -6.12212

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735
No. of obs 727
Mean 60.5596
Standard dev 2.33056
Max value 66.5932
Min value 54.4377

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.2

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 716
Mean 0.180943
Standard dev 5.107398e-02
Max value 0.423969
Min value 0.105925

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 716
Mean 0.134910
Standard dev 2.067707e-02
Max value 0.287313
Min value 0.101425

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 716
Mean 0.343950
Standard dev 0.187923
Max value 0.969543
Min value 0.114395

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

12:34:47 12:37:45 12:40:44 12:43:43 12:46:42
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.2

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 716
Mean 197.459
Standard dev 37.3043
Max value 387.539
Min value 103.124

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 716
Mean 0.111632
Standard dev 7.443704e-03
Max value 0.167222
Min value 9.413579e-02

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 716
Mean 6.04629
Standard dev 5.64112
Max value 72.8133
Min value 0.846040

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.2

LWR VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 688
No. of obs 716
Mean 277.825
Standard dev 6.104381e-02
Max value 277.982
Min value 277.664

LWR VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 689
No. of obs 716
Mean 279.018
Standard dev 5.099459e-02
Max value 279.195
Min value 278.905

LWR I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 690
No. of obs 716
Mean 278.251
Standard dev 5.591709e-02
Max value 278.379
Min value 278.104

12:34:47 12:37:45 12:40:44 12:43:43 12:46:42
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.2

LWR VIS CLR SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 682
No. of obs 716
Mean 97.9445
Standard dev 2.17019
Max value 104.839
Min value 89.1129

LWR VIS RED SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 683
No. of obs 716
Mean 47.9928
Standard dev 0.850660
Max value 51.1420
Min value 43.7264

LWR I/R SIGNAL (WM-2)

Parameter no. 684
No. of obs 716
Mean 496.811
Standard dev 0.478903
Max value 497.974
Min value 495.539

12:34:47 12:37:45 12:40:44 12:43:43 12:46:42

1 second average

TIM (GM)

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.2

UPP VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 679
No. of obs 716
Mean 280.111
Standard dev 4.249567e-02
Max value 280.210
Min value 279.984

UPP VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 680
No. of obs 716
Mean 278.572
Standard dev 3.803247e-02
Max value 278.687
Min value 278.500

UPP I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 681
No. of obs 716
Mean 278.223
Standard dev 4.680375e-02
Max value 278.351
Min value 278.164

12:34:47 12:37:45 12:40:44 12:43:43 12:46:42
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.2

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 716
Mean 728.236
Standard dev 73.7550
Max value 945.797
Min value 378.931

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 716
Mean 338.302
Standard dev 34.4041
Max value 442.442
Min value 135.252

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 716
Mean 1005.94
Standard dev 5.88846
Max value 1037.96
Min value 1000.62

1 second over

TIM (GMT)

12:34:47

12:37:45

12:40:44

12:43:43

12:46:42

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.2

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 716
Mean 186.528
Standard dev 4.59880
Max value 197.683
Min value 168.667

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 716
Mean 291.050
Standard dev 4.47471
Max value 301.472
Min value 274.152

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 716
Mean 7.85583
Standard dev 0.192874
Max value 8.30530
Min value 7.32320

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.2

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 716
Mean 0.452899
Standard dev 8.307976e-03
Max value 0.477412
Min value 0.423801

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 716
Mean 991.041
Standard dev 0.542682
Max value 993.151
Min value 989.727

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 716
Mean 55.1778
Standard dev 1.43540
Max value 59.3089
Min value 50.8531

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.2

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 716
Mean 2.64394
Standard dev 0.103207
Max value 3.01311
Min value 2.42649

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 716
Mean 268.639
Standard dev 0.561372
Max value 270.215
Min value 267.235

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 716
Mean 268.130
Standard dev 0.510996
Max value 269.880
Min value 267.005

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.2

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 716
Mean 277.758
Standard dev 0.133434
Max value 278.173
Min value 277.332

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 716
Mean 273.554
Standard dev 8.455598e-02
Max value 273.889
Min value 273.387

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 716
Mean 229.463
Standard dev 108.153
Max value 280.762
Min value 0.000000

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.2

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 716
Mean -78.5521
Standard dev 1.20730
Max value -75.6582
Min value -82.4362

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 716
Mean 277.864
Standard dev 0.130379
Max value 278.267
Min value 277.448

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 716
Mean 273.780
Standard dev 8.315437e-02
Max value 274.103
Min value 273.619

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.2

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 716
Mean 50.6864
Standard dev 0.113397
Max value 50.8832
Min value 50.4902

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 716
Mean -5.93609
Standard dev 0.230961
Max value -5.53519
Min value -6.33289

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735
No. of obs 716
Mean -61.0823
Standard dev 1.25567
Max value -58.6665
Min value -67.0233

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.2

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 716
Mean 85.2534
Standard dev 5.01572
Max value 101.925
Min value 69.6657

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 716
Mean 8.19955
Standard dev 0.880658
Max value 10.4129
Min value 5.83308

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 716
Mean north -0.669963
Stan dev north 0.700184
Max north 1.71272
Min north -2.45145
Mean east -0.669963
Stan dev east 0.700184
Max east 1.71272
Min east -2.45145

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.1

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 727
Mean 0.176658
Standard dev 4.394685e-02
Max value 0.295878
Min value 0.107089

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 727
Mean 0.134652
Standard dev 1.677241e-02
Max value 0.191433
Min value 0.102153

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 727
Mean 0.320628
Standard dev 0.164012
Max value 0.806417
Min value 0.114186

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.1

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 727
Mean 222.103
Standard dev 34.3720
Max value 341.507
Min value 127.614

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 727
Mean 0.113910
Standard dev 7.470004e-03
Max value 0.138592
Min value 9.670666e-02

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 727
Mean 6.07121
Standard dev 4.58599
Max value 27.0117
Min value 0.870655

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.1

LWR VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 688
No. of obs 727
Mean 277.990
Standard dev 0.413856
Max value 279.435
Min value 277.664

LWR VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 689
No. of obs 727
Mean 279.289
Standard dev 0.434705
Max value 280.837
Min value 278.954

LWR I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 690
No. of obs 727
Mean 278.398
Standard dev 0.416227
Max value 279.988
Min value 278.104

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.1

LWR VIS CLR SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 682
No. of obs 727
Mean 94.3798
Standard dev 2.07104
Max value 98.7903
Min value 79.0323

LWR VIS RED SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 683
No. of obs 727
Mean 46.9877
Standard dev 1.40459
Max value 50.3749
Min value 40.1465

LWR I/R SIGNAL (WM-2)

Parameter no. 684
No. of obs 727
Mean 496.123
Standard dev 1.99616
Max value 498.217
Min value 486.772

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.1

UPP VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 679
No. of obs 727
Mean 280.134
Standard dev 0.328374
Max value 281.479
Min value 279.893

UPP VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 680
No. of obs 727
Mean 278.809
Standard dev 0.348313
Max value 280.096
Min value 278.547

UPP I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 681
No. of obs 727
Mean 278.482
Standard dev 0.406910
Max value 280.041
Min value 278.210

12:21:25 12:24:26 12:27:28 12:30:29 12:33:31

TIME (GMT)

1 second average

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.1

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 727
Mean 793.298
Standard dev 43.9060
Max value 842.070
Min value 0.000000

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 727
Mean 406.240
Standard dev 22.7639
Max value 433.602
Min value 0.000000

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 727
Mean 1003.69
Standard dev 1.21531
Max value 1007.21
Min value 999.522

12:21:25 12:24:26 12:27:28 12:30:29 12:33:31

TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.1

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 727
Mean 186.562
Standard dev 6.34638
Max value 210.702
Min value 165.990

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 727
Mean 290.236
Standard dev 6.30790
Max value 311.880
Min value 268.204

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 727
Mean 7.90935
Standard dev 0.189239
Max value 8.43015
Min value 7.45602

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.1

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 727
Mean 0.452955
Standard dev 8.815236e-03
Max value 0.482622
Min value 0.418785

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 727
Mean 991.038
Standard dev 0.748684
Max value 993.467
Min value 988.193

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 727
Mean 55.0734
Standard dev 1.80587
Max value 59.8745
Min value 50.4984

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.1

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 727
Mean 2.60310
Standard dev 7.342180e-02
Max value 2.84849
Min value 2.41060

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 727
Mean 268.409
Standard dev 0.543449
Max value 269.838
Min value 267.091

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 727
Mean 267.927
Standard dev 0.372589
Max value 269.124
Min value 266.918

12:21:25 12:24:26 12:27:28 12:30:29 12:33:31

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.1

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 727
Mean 277.655
Standard dev 0.149460
Max value 278.084
Min value 277.304

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 727
Mean 273.461
Standard dev 7.782383e-02
Max value 273.775
Min value 273.230

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 727
Mean 280.315
Standard dev 0.124905
Max value 280.597
Min value 279.925

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R3.1

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 727
Mean 62.1232
Standard dev 2.13040
Max value 66.4456
Min value 56.5706

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 727
Mean 277.763
Standard dev 0.145823
Max value 278.172
Min value 277.419

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 727
Mean 273.688
Standard dev 7.442037e-02
Max value 273.995
Min value 273.470

12:21:25 12:24:26 12:27:28 12:30:29 12:33:31

TIME (GMT)

cor ver

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R4

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 480
Mean 30.8584
Standard dev 4.04184
Max value 40.4110
Min value 19.9070

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 480
Mean 4.24827
Standard dev 0.523032
Max value 6.47632
Min value 3.22689

WIND COMP (METRES/S)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 480
Mean north -3.64384
Stan dev north 0.525177
Max north -2.61019
Min north -6.03715
Mean east -3.64384
Stan dev east 0.525177
Max east -2.61019
Min east -6.03715

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R4

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 480
Mean 50.9210
Standard dev 1.783235e-02
Max value 50.9564
Min value 50.8925

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 480
Mean -5.98002
Standard dev 0.216435
Max value -5.60686
Min value -6.35388

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735
No. of obs 480
Mean -14.8106
Standard dev 3.38191
Max value -11.3824
Min value -22.4523

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R4

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 480
Mean -109.238
Standard dev 0.722856
Max value -106.503
Min value -111.246

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 480
Mean 271.512
Standard dev 0.166505
Max value 271.886
Min value 271.144

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 480
Mean 266.011
Standard dev 0.159017
Max value 266.395
Min value 265.713

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R4

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 480
Mean 271.397
Standard dev 0.168790
Max value 271.780
Min value 271.015

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 480
Mean 265.736
Standard dev 0.161046
Max value 266.125
Min value 265.435

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 480
Mean 277.342
Standard dev 2.14829
Max value 278.435
Min value 268.052

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R4

TOTAL WATER CONTENT (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 572
No. of obs 480
Mean 0.261671
Standard dev 3.442985e-02
Max value 0.367159
Min value 0.219344

DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 529
No. of obs 480
Mean 239.540
Standard dev 1.24257
Max value 243.616
Min value 238.129

TOTAL WATER DEW POINT (DEG K)

Parameter no. 725
No. of obs 480
Mean 236.840
Standard dev 1.29688
Max value 240.443
Min value 235.112

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R4

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 480
Mean 0.483300
Standard dev 5.496844e-03
Max value 0.520498
Min value 0.436313

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 480
Mean 697.778
Standard dev 0.499841
Max value 698.529
Min value 695.372

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 480
Mean 54.2652
Standard dev 0.605399
Max value 56.6195
Min value 51.8733

1 second averages

TIME (GMT)

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R4

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 480
Mean 3037.12
Standard dev 5.63090
Max value 3064.24
Min value 3028.67

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 480
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 480
Mean 5.17109
Standard dev 0.148661
Max value 5.47359
Min value 4.70977

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R4

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 480
Mean 806.611
Standard dev 20.5217
Max value 1005.51
Min value 781.977

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 480
Mean 416.572
Standard dev 9.18826
Max value 523.770
Min value 387.192

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 480
Mean 964.485
Standard dev 1.65337
Max value 967.120
Min value 959.431

1 second average

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R4

UPP VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 679
No. of obs 480
Mean 274.855
Standard dev 0.361173
Max value 275.816
Min value 274.593

UPP VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 680
No. of obs 480
Mean 273.091
Standard dev 0.462367
Max value 274.321
Min value 272.678

UPP I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 681
No. of obs 480
Mean 272.600
Standard dev 0.456404
Max value 273.939
Min value 272.249

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R4

LWR VIS CLR SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 682
No. of obs 480
Mean 143.528
Standard dev 35.8015
Max value 237.500
Min value 114.113

LWR VIS RED SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 683
No. of obs 480
Mean 65.2668
Standard dev 18.6615
Max value 115.325
Min value 48.8406

LWR I/R SIGNAL (WM-2)

Parameter no. 684
No. of obs 480
Mean 501.709
Standard dev 3.28706
Max value 506.010
Min value 493.104

13:03:33 13:05:32 13:07:32 13:09:32 13:11:32

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R4

LWR VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 688
No. of obs 480
Mean 272.229
Standard dev 0.389047
Max value 273.397
Min value 271.899

LWR VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 689
No. of obs 480
Mean 273.509
Standard dev 0.405870
Max value 274.704
Min value 273.159

LWR I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 690
No. of obs 480
Mean 272.499
Standard dev 0.381089
Max value 273.691
Min value 272.175

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R4

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 480
Mean 42.5494
Standard dev 11.3268
Max value 83.0675
Min value 12.4265

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 480
Mean 8.657102e-02
Standard dev 8.252776e-03
Max value 0.132122
Min value 7.301873e-02

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 480
Mean 0.513021
Standard dev 1.48610
Max value 11.3889
Min value 4.699856e-02

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R4

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 480
Mean 0.111214
Standard dev $5.419262e-02$
Max value 0.441749
Min value $7.761952e-02$

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 480
Mean $9.686728e-02$
Standard dev $2.612349e-02$
Max value 0.263189
Min value $7.523158e-02$

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 480
Mean 0.159797
Standard dev 0.178962
Max value 1.24395
Min value $8.258468e-02$

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R5

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

No. of obs 486
Mean 38.7162
Standard dev 2.46926
Max value 44.4015
Min value 33.6544

WIND SPEED (METRES/S)

No. of obs 486
Mean 7.45829
Standard dev 0.618158
Max value 8.68722
Min value 6.50295

WIND COMP (METRES/s)

Parameter no. 714,715
No. of obs 486
Mean north -5.81649
Stan dev north 0.551524
Max north -4.68124
Min north -6.98891
Mean east -5.81649
Stan dev east 0.551524
Max east -4.68124
Min east -6.98891

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R5

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 730
No. of obs 486
Mean 51.1196
Standard dev 4.715972e-02
Max value 51.2010
Min value 51.0384

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

Parameter no. 731
No. of obs 486
Mean -5.09378
Standard dev 0.224304
Max value -4.70350
Min value -5.48264

CORRECTED NORTH VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 735
No. of obs 486
Mean 37.2598
Standard dev 0.692820
Max value 38.6154
Min value 33.1554

13:23:06 13:25:07 13:27:08 13:29:09 13:31:11
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R5

CORRECTED EAST VEL (M S-1)

Parameter no. 736
No. of obs 486
Mean 112.045
Standard dev 1.89798
Max value 116.721
Min value 108.900

DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 519
No. of obs 486
Mean 251.501
Standard dev 0.220861
Max value 252.154
Min value 251.231

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 520
No. of obs 486
Mean 244.159
Standard dev 0.103321
Max value 244.339
Min value 243.928

13:23:06 13:25:07 13:27:08 13:29:09 13:31:11
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R5

NON-DEICED IND TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 524
No. of obs 486
Mean 251.348
Standard dev 0.219129
Max value 252.009
Min value 251.078

NON-DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 525
No. of obs 486
Mean 243.795
Standard dev 0.106232
Max value 243.967
Min value 243.550

SURFACE TEMP (DEG K)

Parameter no. 537
No. of obs 486
Mean 276.068
Standard dev 0.291196
Max value 276.536
Min value 274.325

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R5

J/W LWC (G KG-1)

Parameter no. 535
No. of obs 486
Mean 0.522262
Standard dev 5.830351e-03
Max value 0.609663
Min value 0.487844

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

Parameter no. 576
No. of obs 486
Mean 467.615
Standard dev 0.276091
Max value 467.943
Min value 465.826

PITOT-STATIC PRESSUR (MB)

Parameter no. 577
No. of obs 486
Mean 53.5407
Standard dev 1.62566
Max value 57.3548
Min value 50.9900

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R5

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 578
No. of obs 486
Mean 6064.99
Standard dev 4.30311
Max value 6092.87
Min value 6059.87

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

Parameter no. 575
No. of obs 486
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

Parameter no. 574
No. of obs 486
Mean 5.36220
Standard dev 0.111050
Max value 5.75419
Min value 5.13097

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R5

UPP VIS CLR SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 673
No. of obs 486
Mean 834.941
Standard dev 8.38194
Max value 864.270
Min value 814.511

UPP VIS RED SIG (W M-2)

Parameter no. 674
No. of obs 486
Mean 442.540
Standard dev 5.10730
Max value 459.901
Min value 433.160

UPP I/R SIGNAL (W M-2)

Parameter no. 675
No. of obs 486
Mean 958.573
Standard dev 4.18378
Max value 962.726
Min value 945.701

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R5

UPP VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 679
No. of obs 486
Mean 256.276
Standard dev 1.27830
Max value 259.689
Min value 254.888

UPP VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 680
No. of obs 486
Mean 254.363
Standard dev 1.45065
Max value 258.123
Min value 252.724

UPP I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 681
No. of obs 486
Mean 253.754
Standard dev 1.46071
Max value 257.557
Min value 252.159

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R5

LWR VIS CLR SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 682
No. of obs 486
Mean 126.433
Standard dev 1.92695
Max value 130.242
Min value 123.387

LWR VIS RED SIG (WM-2)

Parameter no. 683
No. of obs 486
Mean 52.5421
Standard dev 2.98954
Max value 58.3019
Min value 48.8406

LWR I/R SIGNAL (WM-2)

Parameter no. 684
No. of obs 486
Mean 552.690
Standard dev 3.87059
Max value 556.416
Min value 540.101

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R5

LWR VIS CLR TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 688
No. of obs 486
Mean 253.216
Standard dev 1.42243
Max value 256.871
Min value 251.696

LWR VIS RED TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 689
No. of obs 486
Mean 254.130
Standard dev 1.50795
Max value 258.044
Min value 252.491

LWR I/R TEMP (DEG C)

Parameter no. 690
No. of obs 486
Mean 252.873
Standard dev 1.33381
Max value 256.548
Min value 251.584

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R5

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

Parameter no. 919
No. of obs 486
Mean 7.63175
Standard dev 2.88866
Max value 19.0043
Min value 1.00003

PCASP MEAN RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 920
No. of obs 486
Mean 9.002022e-02
Standard dev 2.040575e-02
Max value 0.229021
Min value 5.810000e-02

PCASP MASS CONTENT (G M-3)

Parameter no. 921
No. of obs 486
Mean 0.103703
Standard dev 0.613200
Max value 10.7789
Min value 1.827459e-03

13:23:06 13:25:07 13:27:08 13:29:09 13:31:11
TIME (GMT)

1 second averages

A444 27-MAR-96

Run no. R5

PCASP MEAN VOL. RAD. (MICRON)

Parameter no. 922
No. of obs 486
Mean 0.106326
Standard dev 5.435695e-02
Max value 0.636119
Min value 5.850191e-02

PCASP MEAN AREAL RAD (MICRON)

Parameter no. 923
No. of obs 486
Mean 9.827528e-02
Standard dev 3.793577e-02
Max value 0.440510
Min value 5.829293e-02

PCASP EFF. RADIUS (MICRON)

Parameter no. 924
No. of obs 486
Mean 0.127174
Standard dev 0.108793
Max value 1.32592
Min value 5.889273e-02

1 second average

TIME (GMT)